

Extra Results ICML Submission 19431

1 [b2Ay] W1/Q1 Class-Conditional Coverage Table

Table 1: **Fitzpatrick (8 clients)**. Class-conditional coverages. We observe that in all cases, FedCF maintains or improves the per-class coverage levels.

	Labels (0-4)									
c	L0		L1		L2		L3		L4	
	FCP	FedCF	FCP	FedCF	FCP	FedCF	FCP	FedCF	FCP	FedCF
0.1	0.997	0.997	0.413	0.413	0.858	0.996	0.035	0.035	0.848	1.000
0.15	0.997	0.997	0.413	0.413	0.858	0.858	0.035	0.035	0.845	1.000
0.2	0.997	0.997	0.413	0.413	0.858	0.858	0.035	0.035	0.845	0.962

	Labels (5-8)							
c	L5		L6		L7		L8	
	FCP	FedCF	FCP	FedCF	FCP	FedCF	FCP	FedCF
0.1	0.095	0.095	0.054	1.000	0.950	1.000	0.706	0.706
0.15	0.095	0.095	0.054	0.054	0.950	0.978	0.706	0.706
0.2	0.095	0.095	0.054	0.054	0.950	0.950	0.706	0.706

2 [b2Ay] W1/Q2b Plots

Figure 1: **ACSIIncome (small)**. These plots show how the coverage gap (cg_curr) varies as we increase λ starting from \hat{q} . As we can see, the relationship is “quasi-monotonic” with $R^2 > 0.8$ for all labels across multiple seeds.

3 [b2Ay] Q4

Table 2: ACSIncome using small split and RAPS – Demographic Parity

c	Classwise Lambdas	(Group, Class)-wise Lambdas
0.1	3.109	2.998
0.15	2.977	2.782
0.2	2.816	2.824

Table 3: Fitzpatrick using 8 clients and RAPS – Demographic Parity

c	Classwise Lambdas	(Group, Class)-wise Lambdas
0.1	5.256	5.215
0.15	3.868	3.662
0.2	3.698	3.606

Table 4: Fitzpatrick using 8 clients and RAPS – Predictive Equality

c	Classwise Lambdas	(Group, Class)-wise Lambdas
0.1	5.258	5.215
0.15	3.872	3.652
0.2	3.524	3.514

Table 5: Pokec using region + gender and DAPS – Demographic Parity

c	Classwise Lambdas	(Group, Class)-wise Lambdas
0.1	3.109	2.881
0.15	3.016	2.878
0.2	2.867	2.867

4 [b2Ay] Q5

Table 6: Distribution of (g, \tilde{y}) for the Pokec-n and Pokec-z clients in the *Pokec* dataset used for intersectional fairness.

Label/Group	0	1	2	3
0	344	435	148	197
1	128	189	51	80
2	96	124	52	68
3	99	78	55	55

5 [b2Ay, qynf] Bullet 1 (Rebuttal Ack.)

Theorem 5.1. *Assuming the same desired closeness criterion, c for all $\tilde{y} \in \mathcal{Y}^+$, and $\gamma_k = \frac{n_k+1}{N+K}$, in order to have non-vacuous prediction sets (i.e., $\lambda < \lambda_{max}$), we need $N^{(g,\tilde{y})} := \sum_{k=1}^K n_k^{(g,\tilde{y})} \geq \frac{2K}{c(N+K)}$ for all $(g, \tilde{y}) \in \mathcal{G} \times \mathcal{Y}^+$.*

Proof. Define the interval width for a particular group label pair as,

$$IW(\lambda, F_m, g, \tilde{y}) := U_{cov}(\lambda, F_m, g, \tilde{y}) - L_{cov}(\lambda, F_m, g, \tilde{y}) = \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_k \left(\frac{(\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda} + 1)}{(n_k + 1)L^{(g,\tilde{y})}} - \frac{\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda}}{(n_k + 1)U^{(g,\tilde{y})}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where U_{cov} and L_{cov} in Theorem 3.1 and Corollary B.5, respectively. We note that we can achieve non-vacuous bounds for each $\tilde{y} \in \mathcal{Y}^+$ if for each $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $IW(\lambda, F_m, g, \tilde{y}) < c$ for some $\lambda < \lambda_{max}$. Observe that if the interval width is greater than c for all λ , then our algorithm cannot find non-vacuous bounds. Also, recall by definition, $L^{(g,\tilde{y})} = N^{(g,\tilde{y})}$ and $U^{(g,\tilde{y})} = N^{(g,\tilde{y})} + K$. Then consider,

$$IW(\lambda, F_m, g, \tilde{y}) = \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_k \left(\frac{(\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda} + 1)}{(n_k + 1)L^{(g,\tilde{y})}} - \frac{\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda}}{(n_k + 1)U^{(g,\tilde{y})}} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$= \frac{1}{N + K} \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\frac{(\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda} + 1)}{L^{(g,\tilde{y})}} - \frac{\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda}}{U^{(g,\tilde{y})}} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$= \frac{1}{N + K} \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\frac{(\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda} + 1)}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})}} - \frac{\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda}}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} + K} \right) \quad (4)$$

Given $\sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y})} \leq \sum_{k=1}^K n_k^{(g,\tilde{y})} = N^{(g,\tilde{y})}$, $\frac{1}{N+K} \left(\frac{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} - \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda}}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})}} - \frac{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} - \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda}}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} + K} \right) \geq 0$. Thus,

$$(4) \leq \frac{1}{N+K} \left[\sum_{k=1}^K \left(\frac{(\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda} + 1)}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})}} - \frac{\alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda}}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} + K} \right) + \left(\frac{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} - \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda}}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})}} - \frac{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} - \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^{(g,\tilde{y});\lambda}}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} + K} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

$$= \frac{1}{N + K} \left(\frac{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} + K}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})}} - \frac{N^{(g,\tilde{y})}}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})} + K} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$= \frac{1}{N + K} \cdot \frac{2N^{(g,\tilde{y})}K + K^2}{N^{(g,\tilde{y})}^2 + N^{(g,\tilde{y})}K} \leq c \quad (7)$$

Thus, we have the interval width, and we want to bound it by c as in (7) $< c$. Solving for the quadratic form and taking the positive root, we arrive at,

$$N^{(g,\tilde{y})} \geq \frac{K}{2c(N+K)} \left(2 - c(N+K) + \sqrt{c^2(N+K)^2 + 4} \right) \quad (8)$$

While (8) is a sufficient quantity for the minimal count, a tight overbound of (8) (for more interpretable bounds) follows as,

$$\frac{K}{2c(N+K)} \left(2 - c(N+K) + \sqrt{c^2(N+K)^2 + 4} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\leq \frac{K}{2c(N+K)} \left(2 - c(N+K) + \sqrt{c^2(N+K)^2 + 4c(N+K) + 4} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$= \frac{K}{2c(N+K)} (2 - c(N+K) + 2 + c(N+K)) \quad (11)$$

$$= \frac{2K}{c(N+K)} \leq N^{(g,\tilde{y})} \quad (12)$$

□

6 [b2Ay] Bullet 2 (Rebuttal Ack.)

Table 7: **Fitzpatrick (8 clients)**. Group-conditional coverages. Note the method does not enforce a minimum per-group coverage requirement.

Group	$c = 0.1$		$c = 0.15$		$c = 0.2$	
	FCP	FedCF	FCP	FedCF	FCP	FedCF
0	0.889	0.910	0.889	0.900	0.889	0.890
1	0.877	0.904	0.876	0.888	0.877	0.878
2	0.897	0.936	0.897	0.915	0.897	0.897
3	0.924	0.955	0.924	0.934	0.924	0.925
4	0.903	0.945	0.903	0.922	0.903	0.903
5	0.911	0.962	0.911	0.930	0.911	0.911

7 [b2Ay] Bullet 3 (Rebuttal Ack.)

Theorem 7.1. Let $\lambda^L \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{Y}|}$ and $\lambda^G \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{Y}| \times |\mathcal{G}|}$ be optimizers for the class-wise and (group, class)-wise formulations of (Fed)CF, respectively. Then let x_{test} represent an unseen covariate, and $\mathbf{g}(x_{test})$ map the covariate to its group. Lastly, let $J_{(y,g)}(\lambda) = \Pr[s(x_{test}, y) \leq \lambda | \mathbf{g}(x_{test}) = g]$ be the CDF function of the conditional score distribution and Lipschitz continuous, with Lipschitz constant $M_{(y,g)}$ over the interval $[\lambda_0, \lambda_{max}]$ —that is for all $v, w \in [\lambda_0, \lambda_{max}]$, $|J_{(y,g)}(v) - J_{(y,g)}(w)| \leq M_{(y,g)}|v - w|$. Then, the efficiency gap between the two (Fed)CF formulations, Δ_{eff} , satisfies,

$$\Delta_{\text{eff}} \leq \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} M_{(y,g)} \left| (\lambda_{(y)}^L - \lambda_{(y,g)}^G) \right| \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{test} = g]. \quad (13)$$

Proof. Observe from the analysis of [Maneriker et al., 2025]¹, the efficiency difference of two prediction sets is quantified as the difference in likelihood of a non-conformity score being less than the threshold for each label. That is,

$$\Delta_{\text{eff}} = \left| \mathbb{E}_{x_{test} \sim \mathcal{X}} \left[\sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} \left(\mathbf{1}[s(x_{test}, y) \leq \lambda_{(y)}^L] - \mathbf{1}[s(x_{test}, y) \leq \lambda_{(y, \mathbf{g}_{test})}^G] \right) \right] \right|, \quad (14)$$

where $\lambda_{(y)}^L$ is the component for class y in λ^L and $\lambda_{(y,g)}^G$ is the component for (y, g) in λ^G . For notational brevity, let $\mathbf{g}_{test} := \mathbf{g}(x_{test})$. Then,

$$\Delta_{\text{eff}} = \left| \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} \left(\Pr[s(x_{test}, y) \leq \lambda_{(y)}^L] - \Pr[s(x_{test}, y) \leq \lambda_{(y, \mathbf{g}_{test})}^G] \right) \right| \quad (15)$$

$$= \left| \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \left(\Pr[s(x_{test}, y) \leq \lambda_{(y)}^L | \mathbf{g}_{test} = g] - \Pr[s(x_{test}, y) \leq \lambda_{(y, \mathbf{g}_{test})}^G | \mathbf{g}_{test} = g] \right) \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{test} = g] \right| \quad (16)$$

$$= \left| \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \left(\Pr[s(x_{test}, y) \leq \lambda_{(y)}^L | \mathbf{g}_{test} = g] - \Pr[s(x_{test}, y) \leq \lambda_{(y, \mathbf{g}_{test})}^G | \mathbf{g}_{test} = g] \right) \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{test} = g] \right| \quad (17)$$

$$= \left| \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \left(J_{(y,g)}(\lambda_{(y)}^L) - J_{(y,g)}(\lambda_{(y, \mathbf{g}_{test})}^G) \right) \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{test} = g] \right| \quad (\text{Definition of CDF}) \quad (18)$$

$$\leq \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \left| J_{(y,g)}(\lambda_{(y)}^L) - J_{(y,g)}(\lambda_{(y, \mathbf{g}_{test})}^G) \right| \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{test} = g] \quad (\text{Triangle Inequality}) \quad (19)$$

$$\leq \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} M_{(y,g)} \left| (\lambda_{(y)}^L - \lambda_{(y, \mathbf{g}_{test})}^G) \right| \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{test} = g]. \quad (\text{Lipschitz Continuity of } J_{(y,g)}) \quad (20)$$

Lastly, we note that since λ^L and λ^G are optimizers to their respective (Fed)CF formulation, for all $y \notin \mathcal{Y}^+$, $\lambda_{(y)}^L = \lambda_{(y, \mathbf{g}_{test})}^G = \lambda_0$. Thus, the bound reduces to,

$$\Delta_{\text{eff}} \leq \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} M_{(y,g)} \left| (\lambda_{(y)}^L - \lambda_{(y, \mathbf{g}_{test})}^G) \right| \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{test} = g] \quad (21)$$

□

¹P. Maneriker et al., *Conformal Prediction: A Theoretical Note and Benchmarking Transductive Node Classification in Graphs*. TMLR 2025.

Theorem 7.2. Assume the setting from Theorem 7.1. Let c be the desired closeness criterion and $cg_{(y)}(\lambda)$ be the coverage gap for the label $y \in \mathcal{Y}^+$ ². Let $\bar{c} = \max_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} cg_{(y)}(\lambda_0)$ be the worst-case coverage gap of the base (federated) conformal predictor with conformal quantile λ_0 . Then, as $\bar{c} \rightarrow c$, $\Delta_{\text{eff}} \rightarrow 0$.

Proof. We will use the same notational convenience of $\mathbf{g}_{\text{test}} := \mathbf{g}(x_{\text{test}})$. Starting from the result of Theorem 7.1, and noting that $\lambda_{(y)}^L, \lambda_{(y,g)}^G \geq \lambda_0$ by construction, we can use Triangle Inequality to get

$$\Delta_{\text{eff}} = \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} M_{(y,g)} \left| (\lambda_{(y)}^L - \lambda_0) - (\lambda_{(y,g)}^G - \lambda_0) \right| \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{\text{test}} = g] \quad (22)$$

$$\leq \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} M_{(y,g)} \left((\lambda_{(y)}^L - \lambda_0) + (\lambda_{(y,g)}^G - \lambda_0) \right) \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{\text{test}} = g] \quad (23)$$

Define $\widehat{cg}_{(y)}(\lambda) := \sup_{\lambda' > \lambda} cg_{(y)}(\lambda')$, giving us $\widehat{cg}_{(y)} \geq cg_{(y)}$. Let $\text{m}cg_{(y)}$ be a continuous, strictly monotonic, envelope of $\widehat{cg}_{(y)}$ s.t. $\text{m}cg_{(y)} \geq cg_{(y)}$. Using $\text{m}cg_{(y)}$ in Algorithm 1 instead of $cg_{(y)}$ yields an upper bound on the true coverage gap, leading to a larger λ_{opt} but still a satisfactory solution. Let $\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L$ and $\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^G$ be the optimizers using $\text{m}cg_{(y)}$ instead of $cg_{(y)}$. Then $\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L > \lambda_{(y)}^L$ and $\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^G > \lambda_{(y)}^G$. This gives us,

$$(23) \leq \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} M_{(y,g)} \left((\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L - \lambda_0) + (\bar{\lambda}_{(y,g)}^G - \lambda_0) \right) \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{\text{test}} = g] \quad (24)$$

$$\leq \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} \left((\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L - \lambda_0) + (\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^G - \lambda_0) \right) M_y, \quad (25)$$

where $M_y = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} M_{(y,g)} \Pr[\mathbf{g}_{\text{test}} = g]$ and $\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^G = \max \{ \bar{\lambda}_{(y,g)}^G \mid g \in \mathcal{G} \}$.

Note that if we take a classwise solution and broadcast it across all groups, we obtain a feasible solution for the (group, class)-wise formulation—essentially replicating the same solution for each group as if no group-specific information were available. As a result, we have that $\bar{\lambda}_{(y,g)}^G \leq \bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L \forall g \in \mathcal{G}$ (i.e., using group information only helps), giving us, $\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^G \leq \bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L$. Thus,

$$(25) \leq 2 \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} (\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L - \lambda_0) M_y. \quad (26)$$

Define $\text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}$ as the inverse of $\text{m}cg_{(y)}$; given a coverage-gap value, it returns the corresponding λ that attains it. Let $c_1, c_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ be such that

$$\text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}(c_1) = \bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L, \quad \text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}(c_2) = \lambda_0.$$

Since $\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L > \lambda_0$, it follows that $c_2 > c_1$. Finally, because $\bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L$ is the optimizer under the closeness criterion, c , we have

$$\text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}(c) = \bar{\lambda}_{(y)}^L,$$

which implies $c = c_1$. Making these substitutions into (26), we obtain

$$(26) \leq 2 \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} (\text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}(c) - \text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}(c_2)) M_y. \quad (27)$$

Let \bar{c} be such that $cg(\lambda_0) = \bar{c}$, and recall that $\text{m}cg(\lambda_0) = c_2$. By definition of $\text{m}cg_{(y)}$, we have $c_2 \geq \bar{c}$, which implies

$$\text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}(\bar{c}) \leq \text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}(c_2).$$

Therefore,

$$(27) \leq 2 \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} (\text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}(c) - \text{m}cg_{(y)}^{-1}(\bar{c})) M_y. \quad (28)$$

Taking the limit as $\bar{c} \rightarrow c$, we see that the efficiency gap tends to zero. In other words, as the base conformal predictor becomes “more fair,” our method approaches the oracle in terms of efficiency. \square

²Note the standard worst-case fairness disparity metric would be $cg(\lambda) := \max_{y \in \mathcal{Y}^+} cg_{(y)}(\lambda)$

8 [b2Ay] Bullet 4 (Rebuttal Ack.)

Figure 2: We run Algorithm 1, which includes *random restarts*—the mechanism we use to continue searching once a new λ_{opt} is found—on a synthetic, jagged function, representing an adversarial coverage gap function. Specifically, we use $\mu = 0.9$, $\eta = 0.1$.